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Research Article

Comparative Analysis of Reddit Posts and ChatGPT-Generated Texts' Linguistic Features: A Short Report on Artificial Intelligence's Imitative Capabilities

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the unprecedented explosion of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly generative AI, has dramatically and drastically altered many human fields, posing queries about how generative AI can imitate human language. Given the newness of generative AI as a controversial phenomenon, there is an urgency to closely examine how its linguistic outputs could mimic human language produced in natural contexts. Hence, in this short report, we discuss the observed similarities and differences in the linguistic features of the subreddit r/Marriage spouse appreciatory posts and ChatGPT-4 outputs. These results were the offshoot of our genre analysis on these two linguistic data sets. Our analysis revealed that ChatGPT-4 generated texts contain impeccable grammar, while the Reddit appreciatory posts have grammatical discrepancies, such as errors in subject-verb agreement, improper punctuation marks, and erroneous capitalization; ChatGPT-4 generated texts have more complex syntactical structure; Reddit dataset utilized more internet jargon, slang, and profanities and seems to be unpredictable and arbitrary in terms of textual length; and ChatGPT-4 outputs appear to overuse emojis while underuse emoticons and tend to use these digital linguistic elements without regard to their proper contexts. In light of these results, we claim that AI-generated texts, although they can mimic human language, this is on a mere surface level, and a closer inspection could uncover distinct variations. We recommend that future studies use more comprehensive and different datasets and continuously employ comparative and contrastive linguistic analysis to further investigate AI's imitative capabilities.

Keywords: *Appreciatory posts, Artificial intelligence, ChatGPT, Imitative capabilities, Linguistic analysis, Reddit, Comparative analysis*

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Introduction

As science and technology continue to evolve, recent discussions have been concerned with the rapid development of software and devices that are starting to think and behave like humans, assessing their influence on society. This emerging trend is referred to as artificial intelligence (AI), which is “the simulation of human intelligence by a system or a machine” (Xu et al., 2021). With a history that goes back from the 1950s, the scope of modern AI has expanded over the years, ranging from robotics and machine learning to speech recognition (Collins et al., 2021). Among these, a particular function of AI that has seen an outstanding breakthrough in impacting various fields of expertise is Natural Language Processing (NLP) — the systematic approach of computers in learning, understanding, and applying language used by humans (Perzzoli et al., 2022; Mah et al., 2022), a feature that is commonly present among smart assistants and chatbots. With the increasing prevalence of digital devices and big data, AI is rapidly evolving while impacting various domains. Most research has highlighted AI's growing significance in eight key areas, including healthcare, sustainable supply chains, and decision-making, as identified through a machine learning-based topic modeling (Dwivedi et al., 2023). Similarly, AI advancements in education have also garnered significant attention. However, as AI expands and its applications grow, the concept is often misunderstood or misused due to a lack of clear definition. In fact, research on AI in the field of education primarily focuses on Adaptive Systems and Personalization in higher education, highlighting the need for more interdisciplinary research and a clearer conceptual understanding of AI (Miller et al., 2024). To prevent confusion, a useful approach is to clarify AI by comparing and contrasting it with human intelligence, particularly in terms of how AI mimics human cognitive abilities (Jarrahi et al., 2022).

The term “imitative capabilities” in the context of AI scholarship and technology has been mentioned for quite a time by some studies (see Andry, 2001; Roberts, 2024; Tideman, 2011). In our study's context, we define imitative capabilities as the ability of an AI tool or software to mimic natural or authentic human

language produced in a non-contrived environment. Given the freshness of large language models' wide public use, the extent to which AI-generated texts imitate human language has yet to be fully unraveled. A few emerging methodological linguistic scaffolds have been employed to study further AI's imitative capacity, such as investigating AI-generated contents' stylistic features (Shah et al., 2023) and linguistic markers (Markowitz et al., 2023). Fascinatingly, ChatGPT-generated texts thus far have been found to be “inherently false and more analytical, more emotional, more descriptive, and less readable” (Markowitz et al., 2023, p. 21). Also, AI-generated outputs differ from human-produced texts in terms of syntactic patterns, vocabulary richness, and recurrence of specific phrases (Shah et al., 2023).

To contribute to the growing studies that compare and contrast AI-generated and human-produced texts, we angled our investigation on Reddit appreciatory posts and the ChatGPT-4 generated outputs. Reddit is a popular free platform that has been increasingly utilized as a data source for a plethora of research studies since it offers datasets from its specific niches or subgroups called “subreddits.” Further, Reddit appreciatory posts can be argued to be a social media avenue worthy to be examined, especially employing linguistic perspectives, given that a substantial percentage of individuals (47%) view social media as a platform for expressing appreciation toward their partners, with 12% expressing these sentiments frequently (Lenhart et al. (2015). In fact, Vogels and Anderson (2020), in an October 2019 survey, reported that 48% of U.S. social media users in committed relationships used these platforms to share or discuss aspects of their relationship or dating life. This indicates a prevalent use of social media as a tool for relationship communication and expression. Finally, Reddit posts' structure makes finding relevant research data easier, removing word limits on posts and offering a qualitatively more expansive dataset (Proferes et al., 2021).

Hence, in this brief report, as an offshoot of the initial genre analysis of subreddit appreciatory posts we executed, we sought to unpack the linguistic features present in the posts and create a closer comparative and contrastive

analysis of these features between Reddit and the ChatGPT-4 generated appreciatory posts. The findings in this report are relevant and significant to the fast-expanding AI scholarship since AI's imitative capabilities have been continuously evolving, and the ways to examine them linguistically have been swiftly emerging but have yet to be fully circumscribed.

Methods

This study's methodology is a byproduct of a study on a comparative genre analysis of selected spouse appreciation posts on Reddit and ChatGPT-4 generated spouse appreciation posts based on the selected posts. The data collection process obtained 75 Reddit posts from the subreddit r/Marriage with the following selection criteria:

1. The posts shall have the highest number of upvotes within the community.
2. It should be uploaded on or before April 2023.
3. No image shall be attached to the post.

Subsequently, the context of these 75 posts was then obtained and attached to White et al.'s (2023) persona pattern, a prompt construction guide that instructs the system to act as a "persona" developed to assist the system in contextualizing its responses, and eventually, serve as the prompts used to generate the 75 ChatGPT-4 generated spouse appreciation posts. During this process, all ChatGPT-4 generated posts were generated across three batches of 20-35 posts in separate chats within 9 hours, involved no fine-tuning, and excluded generation errors such as incomplete responses to highlight the software's basic imitative capabilities.

Upon completion of the data collection involving a total of 150 posts split between the Reddit and ChatGPT-4 categories, apart from the genre analysis done that zeroed in on the structural patterns or the moves in the data, each post was analyzed based on the quantity and use of observable linguistic features such as grammaticality, textual complexity, use of slang and jargon, emojis, and emoticons. Hence, this short article reports on the textual analysis made that renders ancillary purposes to the genre analysis we executed. All findings from each category were promptly recorded and stored within tables for a side-by-side comparison of the differences in the use of linguistic features among the two categories and to gain insight into ChatGPT-4's imitative capabilities.

Result and Discussion

A closer analysis of the linguistic features present in Reddit r/Marriage appreciatory posts and the ChatGPT-4 generated outputs revealed more differences than commonalities. Table 1 lays down these observations. Evidently, ChatGPT-4 generated texts do not contain any ungrammatical construction, given that AI has sophisticated grammar-detecting infrastructures. Also, we noticed more complicated syntactical patterns in ChatGPT-4 produced posts. In the first example in the table under *grammaticality*, it is clear that the use of a semicolon to connect two related sentences shows more grammatical sophistication. On the contrary, certain grammatical errors or deviations were noted in Reddit's appreciatory posts. For example, "*We go to leave and realized it snowed*" contains inconsistent verb tenses in the sentence. Other grammatical discrepancies, such as erroneous capitalization and improper punctuation marks, were also noted.

Table 1. Linguistic Features Comparison of Reddit Posts and ChatGPT-4 Generated Texts

Features	Reddit Spouses' Appreciatory Posts	ChatGPT-4 Generated Texts
Grammaticality	erroneous capitalization; improper punctuation mark; subject-verb agreement	no ungrammatical construction; more complicated syntactical patterns
	<i>Examples:</i> "Having a LO who loves paw patrol even helped him communicate with the some of kids."	<i>Examples:</i> "The decision to become a school bus driver for special needs kids is more

Features	Reddit Spouses' Appreciatory Posts	ChatGPT-4 Generated Texts
	<p>"So today, I got up super early and my husband was gonna take me out to BK for breakfast and I was SO EXCITED. We go to leave and realized it snowed."</p>	<p>than just a job change; it's a commitment to ensuring the safety, comfort, and happiness of children who sometimes struggle to find their place in the world."</p> <p>"I stumbled into the kitchen, still rubbing the sleep from my eyes, to find my spouse standing over the stove, flipping what looked to be the most perfect hash browns I've ever laid eyes on. And let me tell you, they tasted even better than they looked."</p>
Textual complexity	average length: 216 words shortest post: 71 words longest post: 636 words	average length: 359 words shortest post: 187 words longest post: 493 words
Internet jargon/slang	16 Slang* 19 Abbreviations* 7 Profanities*	7 Slang* 3 Abbreviations*
	<p>Examples: "But then I thought about the big picture - how <u>bloody lucky</u> am I?"</p> <p>"...I think it just makes us appreciate the compassion, thoughtfulness, love and overall <u>giveadamn</u> so much more."</p>	<p>Examples: "<u>Yep</u>, you read that right."</p> <p>"When the <u>COVID-19</u> pandemic hit, like many of us, I found myself suddenly unemployed."</p>
Emojis	20*	42*
	<p>Examples: "I love him to death, but he's making me burn out on my favorite snacks. 😭"</p> <p>"But we hung in there and now we're in the good times. 😊"</p>	<p>Examples: "The Most Amazing Surprise from the Best Spouse Ever 🌹🌟"</p> <p>"Keep spreading the love, folks! 💕👉"</p>
Emoticons	6*	1*
	<p>Examples: "All I've got to say is whether you like your SO's snoring or not I wish you all the best for the future :)"</p> <p>"Thanks for letting me get out my gratitude as he doesn't seem to think this is the miracle that I view it as. :D"</p>	<p>Examples: "P.S. If anyone's looking for an amazing hash brown recipe, hit me up. I might be persuaded to share the secret to these crispy delights. ;)"</p>

Note: * = number of instances

In terms of textual complexity, with a focus on the posts' length, ChatGPT-4 generated appreciatory posts are longer, with an average length of 359 words. However, Reddit posts, given the fact that they were produced by humans, tend to be more flexible, unpredictable, and arbitrary since the Reddit dataset contains both the shortest post and the longest appreciatory post, with 71 words and 636 words, respectively.

As for the internet jargon and slang, the Reddit dataset contains more of them, with a total of 16 instances of slang, 19 abbreviations, and seven profanities. This lucidly indicates that ChatGPT-4 generated texts lack natural human expressions. The absence of profanities in its dataset is also proof of it. Nevertheless, the ChatGPT-4 produced posts have more emojis than the Reddit dataset. In this case, we argue that ChatGPT-4 tends to exaggerate the use of emojis to attempt to mimic human digital linguistic habits. And since it has been trained using a voluminous amount of human linguistic data, emojis rarely used in typical social media posts have also been noticed. For instance, the use of *sparkle* ✨ and *diamond* 💎 in the posts. Moreover, it seems that ChatGPT-4 merely captures the general contexts where these emojis may be used, not really the specific situations in which they may be required. In the post *"Keep spreading the love, folks! ❤️💎,"* although a diamond symbol generally connotes marriage, a more appropriate and contextualized symbol relative to the message of the actual post can render it more human-like. In comparison, Reddit appreciatory posts utilize emojis that enhance the message the poster wanted to convey. For example, the use of 😂 clearly adds a tinge of humor to the sentence to which it is attached: *"I love him to death, but he's making me burn out on my favorite snacks 😂."* In addition, the use of punctuation marks and symbols readily available on the computer's keyboard [e.g. :)] that serve as emoticons is more apparent in the Reddit dataset. In fact, Reddit's appreciatory dataset has six of them, while ChatGPT-4 has only one. This reveals that the latter dataset seems to have favored the use of more sophisticated emoticons, which suggests that it is more mechanical or automatic, a distinct trait of artificiality.

Ostensibly, our study's findings lend support to Shah et al.'s claims (2023Andr) that texts produced by AI vary significantly from human-produced linguistic outputs in terms of syntax, vocabulary richness, and patterns of specific phrases. In terms of syntax, the ChatGPT-4 dataset has more complex syntactical patterns and noticeably richer vocabulary. Moreover, although our study utilized a dataset exclusive to a specific community of social media users—that is, the r/Marriage subreddit—the analysis confirms that by dissecting the vocabulary richness, sentence structure, word length, and punctuations, the distinctive differences between the human-produced texts and AI-generated outputs could be pointed out (Shah et al., 2023). For instance, the words or lexicon utilized in ChatGPT-4 texts were more elaborate and repetitive, an observation that is in congruence with Markowitz et al.'s (2023) claim that AI-generated content is "more emotional [and] more descriptive" but "less readable" (p. 21). Given these linguistic findings, a more encompassing comparative analysis of AI-produced texts and human digital language should be further sought.

Conclusion

With the linguistic analysis done to the subreddit and ChatGPT-4 generated appreciatory posts as an offshoot part of the genre analysis we conducted, we found that subreddit appreciatory posts in comparison with the ChatGPT-4 generated texts vary in terms of grammaticality, textual complexity, internet jargon/slang, emojis, and emoticons. We observed that AI-generated content has impeccable grammar, more elaborate syntactical structure, and repetitive and unmindful use of internet emoticons. With this, we conclude that although AI can mimic human language, this is, at the moment, only on a surface level; hence, a deeper inspection of its linguistic elements could disclose its artificial pretense. Moreover, we conclude that comparative and contrastive linguistic analysis of a wider dataset and coverage could be a potential tool to examine AI's imitative capabilities further as AI continuously impacts many human fields and endeavors and has raised ambivalent opinions and projections from experts and the general public who are

essentially the drivers and data-suppliers of AI's prowess per se.

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